

Identifying expectations and views of stakeholders regarding the SHIFT-HUB service offer

Adamantios Koumpis¹, Paul Stefanut² and Odysseas Spyroglou^{2,3}

¹ Institute for Biomedical Informatics, University Hospital Cologne, Cologne, Germany

² Booster Labs, Paris, France

³ Dublin City University, Dublin, Ireland

0. Preamble

As part of the SHIFT-HUB consortium meeting held in Stuttgart on 30 and 31 March, we have organised during the second day a workshop to identify and explore issues related to the nature of the project offerings and innovations with respect to our aim of building and operating a smart health innovation and technologies Hub¹.

Below we present some background information about the project context and then we present the results.

1. Brief background on the SHIFT-HUB context

Dating back to its origins in 1980s of the corporate stakeholder theory [Freeman, 2010], it is now widely used to refer to 'stakeholders' in a variety of contexts and application fields, as it provides expressive power and the means to:

1. Identify and describe all interested and affected parties in the deployment of a technology;
2. Acknowledge stakeholders have legitimate interests in technology;
3. Affirm that all stakeholders have intrinsic value, even if their concerns do not align with the concerns of the technology producers;
4. Identify the responsibilities of parties with relation to a given process [Donaldson, 1995].

1.1. Why narratives?

Market and stakeholder needs analysis is crucial for the successful project implementation and achievement of our objectives. For this reason, we preferred to avoid building it based on the results of desk research and supported a more hands-on approach that gave emphasis to acquire narratives directly from the field and practitioners and conveying all acquired information in suitable epics and user stories.

The aim of SHIFT-HUB is to establish a pan-European Smart Health Innovation Hub bringing together a rich network of multidisciplinary stakeholders across the dimensions of the quadruple helix

¹ In the following we refer only to the 'Hub'.

[Farinha, 2012], with the mission to facilitate the development, ensure the promotion and foster the uptake of Smart Health technologies and services.

Figure 1: The SHIFT-HUB ecosystem with the quadruple helix interactions

As Donaldson and Preston identified in their seminal paper, '[T]he stakeholder theory has been advanced and justified in the management literature on the basis of its descriptive accuracy, instrumental power, and normative validity. These three aspects of the theory, although interrelated, are quite distinct; they involve different types of evidence and argument and have different implications [Donaldson, 1995]. It is exactly for this reason that we promoted the case of posing importance to the notion of stories.

The above is coherent also with the aims of the SHIFT-HUB project, according to which by putting a strong community of emerging digital technologies providers, and with the support of practitioners and the healthcare institutions they represent, at the service of patients and citizens, SHIFT-HUB may contribute to better coordination and stronger cooperation among the various public and private stakeholders of the Health and Care ecosystems, not only in each member country but also at the pan-European level as a whole.

We consider that the approach we promote is very close to the core first thesis of the aforementioned paper of Donaldson and Preston according to which '[t]he stakeholder theory is unarguably descriptive' and presents abstractions and models that can be 'tested for descriptive accuracy' and which can 'also serve as a framework for testing any empirical claims'.

With respect to SHIFT-HUB the central underlying element relates to ecosystems that address technology development and experimentation that will result in patient-centric and community-driven pilots, offering secure access to anonymized data for application development and paving the way toward the future federated European Health Data Space.

1.2. The relevance of new business models in the emerging European Health Data Space (EHDS)

Developing new and innovative business models will become important to achieve growth and sustainability in the European Health Data Space (EHDS).

The European Commission's proposal for a regulation on a European Health Data Space aims to improve individuals' access to and control of their electronic personal data (primary use), while facilitating data re-use for societal good across the EU (secondary use). Grounded in the EU data strategy, which mentions health as one of the nine European common data spaces, it cuts across several other EU policy priorities, such as the health union and the digital single market.

The proposal establishes a set of rules, infrastructure and governance mechanisms to promote both primary and secondary uses of electronic health data, while ensuring data protection and strengthening cybersecurity.

From an infrastructures' perspective, to link and explore fragmented data of different types, disease areas and provenance which are scattered in repositories and databases across Europe requires, apart from a solid governance, also clear and non-conventional business models for data ingestion and exploitation by public and private organizations.

1.3. Stories shall lead to novel model business blueprints

In the light of the above a major challenge for the SHIFT-HUB project will be to *develop business model blueprints* that we discuss and validate as part of workshop series at the mid and before the end of the project.

At the first phase members of the consortium will participate only in these workshops; at a second phase external actors and stakeholders will be included.

Again, strategic design and market research methods like Kano modelling for user acceptance may be used in order to come up with optimal business models. Ethical, Legal, Social Implications (ELSI) aspects, as well as future and emerging trends at social, business and policy level need to be taken into account. Especially for the ethical use of the system this is expected to play a central role in defining the business model blueprints. Results will be presented as part of the 'Stakeholders mapping and needs' in Deliverable 5.1 and situated with existing healthcare and healthtech research and innovation ecosystems.

2. Questions set to facilitate the narratives collection

[Kavvadia 2022] states that '[t]o understand the organization as a functioning whole, in interaction with its context, at the specific points in time corresponding to the crafted business models. In other words, what were the primary objectives and resources, and how have they been used to achieve the organizational objectives and assess the degree to and ways in which the objectives have been achieved? Further, who were the primary actors and stakeholders, and what was their role? What was the interaction with the organization with its context, and how did the context shape organizational agency? In the event that the research question concerns a specific organizational activity, the business model can alternatively allow the focus to be on the relevant aspects of the particular organizational activity through refinement to increase the level of detail to the desired level, matching the research needs.' (p. 105)

We have below identified a set of (open answer) questions that come from the literature and which we used as part of our preparation for the first workshop within the consortium to identify some primary patterns:

Nr.	Questions	Sources
1.	Which factors determine the business models of organizations operating in a smart health data ecosystem?	[D'Hauwers, 2022]

2.	How are the business model of real-world data ecosystems constructed?	[D'Hauwers, 2022]
3.	How do organizations retain control over their data and design governance in inter-organizational relationships while deconstructing data silos?	[Abraham, 2019]
4.	How are value and trust created in data collaborations?	[Abraham, 2019]
5.	How can companies propose, create, deliver, and capture value while protecting privacy in a sustainable way?	[Rezac, 2022]
6.	Based on the proposition that privacy can be only protected when a business model is economically feasible, how can start-ups and entrepreneurs that put privacy protection and social values as a keystone of their existence become financially stable?	[Rezac, 2022]
7.	What are the drivers and challenges of their efforts?	[Rezac, 2022]
8.	What are the characteristics of their ecosystems and their relationship with "oligopolies" and centralized mega-corporations?	[Rezac, 2022]
9.	How do they interact with incumbents when entering established ecosystems?	[Rezac, 2022]

While all questions presented above are important and relevant, they are of rather academic nature and thus would be not helpful to acquire opinions and views regarding the project offer. For this reason, we have transformed them into questions that might better fit into an interactive workshop, which we present below.

3. The workshop questions

The first question we addressed was:

3.1. First things first...

The ecosystems we aspire to support and promote in Smart Health are... related with start ups

- YES
- NO
- MAYBE

The rationale for this first question was to see how much the notion and ideas of ecosystems and the hub are (or are not) related to start-ups.

It is a common place that people associate novelties and innovations and a 'thinking outside the box' mentality and attitude mainly to start-ups usually ran by young entrepreneurs. This is not always true, as many public or large and / or established private organisations bring innovations to the market and relate themselves to many game-changing products and services.

So this first question aimed to 'test' if there is some positive prejudice against start-ups as core-related to ecosystems.

The ecosystems we aspire to support and promote in Smart Health are... Related with start ups 14

From the results above, we see that the majority of the workshop participants see a high relevance to start-ups.

The second question we addressed was:

The ecosystems we aspire to support and promote in Smart Health are... related with deep techs

- YES
- NO
- MAYBE

Again, and same as for the first question, our aim was to receive inputs regarding the attitude of the workshop participants on the nature of the companies and entities in general related to the Hub. What the question intentionally and deliberately leaves out is what the exact understanding of the participants was for deep techs.

The ecosystems we aspire to support and promote in Smart Health are... Related with deep techs 14

From the results above, we see that the majority of the workshop participants – and with an increase in comparison to the previous question, see a high relevance of the innovation ecosystems to deep techs.

The third question we addressed was:

The ecosystems we aspire to support and promote in Smart Health are... related with medtechs / healthtechs

- YES
- NO
- MAYBE

Same as with the questions before, here our aim was to see if people associated the 'Hub' with only or mainly healthtechs and medtechs, or allowed also for other types of ventures.

The ecosystems we aspire to support and promote in Smart Health are... Related with medtechs / healthtechs 14

Again, and same as with the previous question, from the results above it is obvious that the majority of the workshop participants relate the aspired ecosystems with medtechs and healthtechs.

The fourth question we addressed was at some extent a control question for the previous one while also extending the scope of the associated entities, in order to confirm that any type of health- or medicine-related entrepreneurship, apart from healthtechs or medtechs, is relevant to the 'Hub':

The ecosystems we aspire to support and promote in Smart Health are... related with any type of health-care and medicine related entrepreneurship

- YES
- NO
- MAYBE

The ecosystems we aspire to support and promote in Smart Health are...
Related with any type of health-care and medicine related entrepreneurship ¹⁴

The results we acquired were confirming that the expectations from the side of the workshop participants they have for the ecosystems that the 'Hub' shall foster are highly related to health-care and medicine related entrepreneurship.

3.2. On hubs and ecosystems

The set of questions in this second part of the questionnaire aims to get some closer and deeper insight into the workshop participants' understanding of the nature and functionality of the 'Hub'. While the questions may appear as generic, during the workshop we achieved a good level of understanding amongst the participants, because of the discussions and the presentations that have taken place before. So while these questions as they appear here seem as if they lack or are disconnected from a specific, context, this is not the case at all.

The first question in this part of the questionnaire aimed to check how central the workshop participants think it is the concept of the ecosystem:

The concept of ecosystems is central to our project project

- YES
- NO
- MAYBE

The concept of ecosystems is central to our project project15

Yes

No

Maybe

From the results we were happily surprised (and a bit unprepared for this) on how almost unanimous the workshop participants agree that the notion of ecosystems is central to the project.

The second question aimed to help us get a clearer picture of the understanding that the workshop participants have for the concept of the 'Hub', by providing an assertive sentence that the workshop participants would agree with or not:

How do you understand the concept of a Hub? Like: our project is a **hub** between stakeholders with needs and owners of potential solutions, to allow for matchmaking.

- YES
- NO
- MAYBE

How do you understand the concept of a Hub: Is our project a hub between stakeholders with needs and owners of potential solutions, to allow for matchmaking ?15

Yes

No

Maybe

The results support the idea of the Hub as a mediator – a pattern that will become more apparent in the third part of the questionnaire where we have the opportunity to test specific scenarios.

Again, here we aim to acquire the understanding of the workshop participants by offering a pair of one assertive and one non-assertive sentences regarding the functions of the 'Hub':

How do you understand the concept of a Hub? Like: we support **any type of connections** in health-related value chains – so **not** only simple matchmaking.

- YES
- NO
- MAYBE

How do you understand the concept of a Hub: Do we support any type of connections in health-related value chains – so not only simple matchmaking ?

16

Yes

63 %

No

6 %

Maybe

31 %

The pattern of the results to this question was very close to the previous question, which helps us see that the workshop participants follow some pattern of expectations that the SHIFT-HUB service offer.

The next question is aiming to identify the understanding of the workshop participants regarding value creation as a result of the 'hubbing' process, in terms of all possible functions and services related to or associated with the 'Hub'.

Again here the main idea is to see if the 'Hub' is perceived as an enabler or amplifier to value that has been or is created elsewhere (e.g. a single start-up or an ecosystem), or it is itself involved in the Value Creation process as such.

Value creation is the result of the 'hubbing' process

- YES
- NO
- MAYBE

Value creation is the result of the 'hubbing' process?15

Yes

No

Maybe

Regarding the results of this question, we have to admit that we expected the workshop participants to see value creation as one of the main results of the hubbing process. However, the participants expressed in their majority uncertainty ('Maybe').

This is both understandable and traceable, as we need from our side as consortium to provide clear concepts for both:

- What *exactly* is the value created as result of the 'Hub' and
- What *exactly* is / offers the 'Hub'.

This concretisation of our offer is facilitated in the next section where we present specific scenarios on what *exactly* could form part of the SHIFT-HUB service offer.

The next and also the last question of this part of the questionnaire can be regarded as a control question in terms of trying out to refine the workshop participants attitude and idea against the concept of value creation: do we regard the 'Hub' as a mediator only for the value creation process, or may the 'Hub' also own the value it creates?

What is the role of the hub in the value creation process? Can also 'own' the value it creates

- YES
- NO
- MAYBE

What is the role of the hub in the value creation process? Can also 'own' the value it creates 14

Yes

 14 %

No

 7 %

Maybe

 79 %

Same and also with a stronger preference, the workshop participants voted 'Maybe' for the value ownership question. Again, and same as mentioned before, it is with us the challenge to provide convincing concepts and examples of what the project can offer.

3.3. Let's rate some scenarios...

This third part of the questionnaire that also appeared to me more interesting and exciting to the workshop participants as it involved the validation of some hypothetical scenarios.

We chose to develop two scenarios: one coming from the side of the needs ('demand' side) which is represented in the consortium by our partner Coalition Of Patients Organisation With Chronic Disease (COPAC), and a second one related to the 'supply side' represented in the consortium by several partners (UKK, AUTH, UPORTO, ...). However, for the needs of the scenarios we came up to the persona of Elisio.

We have decided to check two aspects for our scenarios: whether the workshop participants regard them as *relevant* to the project, and independently to this, whether they regard them as typical.

The idea is to check the understanding of the workshop participants regarding what they see as plausible and likely scenarios for the 'Hub' and what they see as most expected.

To this relevance may be associated with representativeness, while typical may be associated to the most usual characteristics or feature, demonstrating also the most usual (expected) qualities or characteristics of the 'Hub'.

A patients' organisation in country X decides to develop some **Challenges** for solutions they may need to support needs of e.g. patients with chronic diseases. They publish their Challenges through the hub and the service offer mechanism to find potential **Solvers**. Do you consider this as a **relevant** scenario for the project?

1. NOT RELEVANT AT ALL
2. NOT RELEVANT
3. RATHER RELEVANT
4. RELEVANT
5. VERY RELEVANT

A patients' organisation in country X develops Challenges for solutions they need to support eg. patients with chronic diseases. They publish their Challenges in our hub to find potential Solvers (service offer mechanism). 15
Is this as a relevant scenario?

We see that the workshop participants understand this scenario as rather very relevant to the project context.

Independently of what you selected in the previous question, we assume that you considered the previous scenario as relevant. Based on this, how much **typical** do you consider it for the project?

- NOT TYPICAL AT ALL
- NOT TYPICAL
- RATHER TYPICAL
- TYPICAL
- VERY TYPICAL

Independently of what you selected in the previous question, we assume that you considered the previous scenario as relevant. Based on this, how much typical do you consider it for the project? 15

However, the same workshop participants see that this scenario should not be seen as a mainstream scenario for the 'Hub'.

The aforementioned patients' organisation decides to proceed with some ideas provided by one or two of the **Solvers**. Do you consider this as a **relevant** entrepreneurship promotion and support scenario for the project?

1. NOT RELEVANT AT ALL
2. NOT RELEVANT
3. RATHER RELEVANT
4. RELEVANT
5. VERY RELEVANT

The aforementioned patients' organisation decides to proceed with some ideas provided by one or two of the Solvers. Do you consider this as a relevant entrepreneurship promotion and support scenario for the project?

14

Score: 4.8 ★

Here the workshop participants again see as very relevant outcome of the 'Hub' service offer that a patients' organisation will proceed towards realisation and implementation of some ideas with one or two of the Solvers.

Again and independently of what you selected in the previous question, we assume that you considered the previous scenario as relevant. Based on this, how much **typical** do you consider it for the project?

- NOT TYPICAL AT ALL
- NOT TYPICAL
- RATHER TYPICAL
- TYPICAL
- VERY TYPICAL

Independently of what you selected in the previous question, we assume that you considered the previous scenario as relevant. Based on this, how much typical do you consider it for the project? 14

And similar to the previous pair of questions, the workshop participants raise their doubts on whether this scenario should be regarded as mainstream or most expected.

The next question raises an interesting point which in aspects related to co-creation has no easy or obvious answers – it is about ownership:

In the same scenario: the patients' organisation (acting as a **Challenger**) together with the **Solver(s)** develops a plan for financing the solution. Who should own the solution?

- THE CHALLENGER
- THE SOLVER
- BOTH – IT IS ALL ABOUT VALUE CO-CREATION. Noone should feel or get treated unfairly!

In the same scenario: the patients' organisation (acting as a Challenger) together with the Solver(s) develops a plan for financing the solution. Who should own the solution? 13

THE CHALLENGER

 0 %

THE SOLVER

 46 %

BOTH – IT IS ALL ABOUT VALUE CO-CREATION. Noone should feel or get treated unfairly!

 54 %

The majority expressed a preference towards a synergetic and participatory understanding of the ownership issue. However, a fairly high amount of participants voted for the solvers to be regarded as 'owners' of the solution. We are convinced that the issue of ownership can be more complicated and, subject to the particular presentation, may also include the 'Challengers' as also potential owners of a solution for a number of reasons (: they have identified the need, they may have also financed the solution, hence they have an increased say in also owning or co-owning it).

Let's consider a different scenario of scientific medtech entrepreneurship: Elisio is Professor and a top grade researcher. He is researching in his laboratory in the university and all data acquired by his research is used for publishing purposes and also for facilitating his future research. Do we consider the hub as an **enabler** for helping Elisio create new value for purely entrepreneurial and commercial activities, e.g. by means of helping him establish a start-up / spin-out at his university technology park, incubator or accelerator?

- YES
- NO
- MAYBE
- DON'T KNOW

A different scenario (scientific medtech entrepreneurship): Elisio is Professor and a top grade researcher. He is researching in uni lab and all data acquired by his research is used for publishing purposes and also for facilitating his future research.

14

YES

NO

 7 %

MAYBE

 14 %

DO NOT KNOW

 7 %

With no doubt, the workshop participants regard the 'Hub' as a natural Enabler for Elisio's healthtech / medtech driven entrepreneurial and commercial activities.

Do you consider the case of Elisio's case as a **relevant** entrepreneurship promotion and support scenario for the project?

1. NOT RELEVANT AT ALL
2. NOT RELEVANT
3. RATHER RELEVANT
4. RELEVANT
5. VERY RELEVANT

Do you consider the case of Elisio's case as a relevant entrepreneurship promotion and support scenario for the project?

14

Score: 4.4 ★

The workshop participants also undoubtedly regard this scenario as very representative for the 'Hub'.

Independently of what you selected in the previous question, we assume that you considered Elisio's case scenario as relevant. Based on this, how much **typical** do you consider it for the project?

- NOT TYPICAL AT ALL
- NOT TYPICAL
- RATHER TYPICAL
- TYPICAL
- VERY TYPICAL

Independently of what you selected in the previous question, we assume that you considered Elisio's case scenario as relevant. Based on this, how much typical do you consider it for the project? 14

However, the workshop participants express little reservations on how typical the Elisio scenario can be for the 'Hub'. However, their reservations are less in comparison to the ones expressed for the previous 'demand' side scenario with the patients association.

This is an outcome that we have not expected and we regard that it is worth to examine in depth, as it seems that the understanding for the 'Hub' may relate to offering a supply side driven ecosystem creation. We commit to investigate this further and also ground it with discussions with stakeholders.

3.4. Data, technology, business models

We planned to have a more elaborate fourth section in our questionnaire during the workshop, where the focus would be on the different type of solutions and service concepts that can be seen as part of the 'Hub' offer.

We changed however our idea as we see many good reasons to stay with the questions before we hasten to provide answers. *We are – based also on our experiences – convinced that the reason for many projects' failure is that they tend to jump to the solutions, before having sufficiently researched in the field of their intervention.*

It is all about Data in the hubbing process: actors that **own** data, actors that have know-how and technologies on how to **process** and **manage** data, those that **need** (to use) data. All different scenarios that are relevant or typical in the hub need to be related with data.

- YES

- NO
- MAYBE
- NOT NECESSARILLY
- DON'T KNOW

It is all about Data in the hubbing process: actors that own data, actors that have know-how and technologies on how to process and manage data, those that need (to use) data. 13

YES

NO

MAYBE

NOT NECESSARILLY

DON'T KNOW

Here again, one may have wished to receive straight 'Yes' or 'No' answers to the question. Also, it was necessary to provide to the workshop participants an explanation for the difference between 'maybe' and 'not necessarily'. 'Not necessarily' means, according to the information provided to the workshop participants, that the 'hubbing' process and the 'Hub' service offer should *not* be related or defined with respect to data science – or, as one might expect – AI applications and functionalities.

For a more precise answer to what exactly is or could be the 'hubbing' process and the 'Hub' functionality we should need to continue our communications with stakeholders. To this, the workshop modality we have started with the Stuttgart workshop is considered as very suitable and we shall continue building on it.

4. Project relevant information

This working report is part of our activities in WP5 and WP3 regarding 'Stakeholder and community engagement' and SHIFT-HUB service offer' respectively, and in particular Task 3.1 'Stakeholder promotion, cooperation and procurement opportunities' and Task 5.1 concerning 'Market and stakeholder needs analysis'.

All sli.do results presented in the Figures above can be found at this link [here](#).

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